

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

GLOBAL WARMING, COP-29 AND AZERBAIJAN

Elshad Gurbanov¹

Sanubar Aslanova²

¹Baku State University

²Azerbaijan State Pedagogical University

Abstract

Global warming is one of the most important environmental problems of the modern era. The effects of climate change are observed in the form of global warming of the atmosphere, rising sea levels and an increase in natural disasters. In this context, various events are being held at the international level, and COP-29 (Conference of the Parties on Climate Change) is one of the main platforms of this process. Azerbaijan is also one of the countries affected by the effects of global warming and, while participating in international initiatives, is trying to formulate its own national strategy. The abstract analyzes these issues in detail and discusses Azerbaijan's position, contributions and challenges at COP-29. The role of the country and future strategies in ecological, economic and political contexts are also the main focus of this article.

Keywords: COP-29, global warming, climate change, Azerbaijan, sustainable development, environmental policy

One of the main challenges of the 21st century is ensuring ecological balance. This includes limiting the intensive exploitation of natural resources, oil, gas and coal production, giving priority to renewable energy sources, green and blue economy, efficient use of water resources, reducing carbon dioxide emissions, recycling and other issues.

Plants are the basis of the life of all living things on the planet, the organic world and living life began with plants. The plant world has the ability to directly use sunlight thanks to the unique process of photosynthesis, which creates the appearance of the Earth we observe. It is plants that provide the Earth with oxygen and thereby act as the driving force of evolution. They are a rich reserve of organic matter and a very valuable resource. The vegetation cover of each region is constantly changing as a result of the continuous complex influence of environmental factors of the territory. These changes occur depending on the physical and geographical conditions of the territory, global warming, and disruption of the ecological balance of the atmosphere.

The impact of global warming directly on flora, indirectly on human health, and on the living ecosystem as a whole is constantly in the focus of humanity.

As technology develops, global climate change is one of the main problems that concern florists and ecologists around the world. The scale of natural disasters resulting from anomalous climate change continues to increase from year to year. Due to the impact of global warming, long-term droughts and desertification occur in regions, the plant world completely disappears or decreases, and the ecological balance and energy balance on Earth are disrupted.

According to scientists, as a result of the complete melting of continental glaciers and the expansion of water from heat, the level of the oceans will increase by 70-80 centimeters compared to the present, coastal settlements, where millions of people currently live, will be flooded, which will change the annual trajectories of cyclones and anticyclones and intensify

climate change, thus leading to the extinction of many plant species.

The potential role of plants in saving the Earth from catastrophic climate change is known to mankind. However, as a result of some recent research conducted by world ecologists and florists, it has become clear that the plants that make up the Earth's vegetation cover are capable of absorbing more carbon dioxide released into the atmosphere as a result of human activity than previously thought. Researchers have determined that a properly constructed climate model used to determine the effects of global warming, taking into account some features of the photosynthesis process, predicts an increase in the absorption of carbon dioxide by plants by the end of the 21st century. For example, it is possible to determine how efficiently carbon dioxide can move in the leaf, how plants adapt to temperature changes, and how nutrients are distributed.

For many years, human activity has caused irreversible damage to the environment. A few years ago, humanity lived by the principle of "whatever happens after us". Fortunately, this trend has changed. Thus, the exploitation of ecosystem resources is limited to a level that does not harm the restoration of natural systems. The development of a green economy is direct evidence of this. A green economy is an economic development model that assumes a responsible attitude of people to natural resources. It is aimed at finding a reasonable compromise between increasing prosperity and protecting natural resources.

Developed countries are raising funds for financial assistance to developing countries to help them adapt and reduce the impact of climate change. Thus, everyone thinks that it is possible to save plant species through measures to reduce the impact of climate change on the world's flora.

In order to stop rapid global warming, tame extreme weather conditions, slow down the rate of melting glaciers and save the biosphere, selected intelligent people must find a way out. Since vegetation is constantly changing as part of a living ecosystem,

people must recognize plants, and experts must develop measures to protect and restore the flora of the areas they live in.

2024 is significant as Azerbaijan, a fossil fuel producer and exporter, will host the 29th session of the Conference of the Parties to the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change (COP29). At this time, the leadership of the Republic of Azerbaijan has set itself the goal of demonstrating its strategy for taking serious measures on climate change. COP29 will be a global forum where important steps will be taken together to discuss and solve environmental problems. Baku will be the center of the world for two weeks, and the city will welcome approximately 70-80 thousand foreign guests. Hosting COP29 in Azerbaijan is, first of all, a recognition by the UN of Azerbaijan's fulfillment of its climate commitments. In addition, hosting COP29 in Azerbaijan signals recognition of political and economic stability in the country at the UN level. The decision to host COP29 in Baku also expresses global support for Azerbaijan's green energy policy. Accordingly, by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan Ilham Aliyev, 2024 was declared the "Year of Solidarity for a Green World" in Azerbaijan. Being an oil and gas country, Azerbaijan has currently identified the creation of green energy types and the transportation of green energy to world markets as a new priority direction of its energy policy. The export of electricity produced on the basis of renewable and green energy has led to the beginning of a new era in Azerbaijan's energy strategy. The implementation of the project in Azerbaijan will create broad opportunities for achieving achievements in the fields of ecology, economy, innovation and technology.

The political and economic advantages that COP29 can bring to Azerbaijan are significant in terms of strengthening the country's position in the regional and international arena. Within the framework of this event, Azerbaijan, by actively participating in the fight against global climate change, gains the opportunity to draw attention to the important problems facing the modern world.

On the political level, holding COP29 attracts the attention of Azerbaijani leaders and diplomatic missions, increasing the country's positive image in the international community. This process creates conditions for a wide discussion of Azerbaijan's environmental policy, energy efficiency and efficient management of resources.

From an economic point of view, organizing the conference helps to attract investment to the local economy and provide an opportunity for the development of the tourism sector. At the same time, COP29 serves the transfer of green technologies, the implementation of innovative projects and the expansion of the sphere of interest of foreign investors. As a result, Azerbaijan's role in global climate policy further strengthens its economy and international relations.

Global warming and climate change are among the most serious environmental problems facing humanity. International conferences such as COP-29 are important in terms of organizing countries' joint fight

against these problems and identifying specific measures. Azerbaijan, as an active participant in this process, is trying to contribute to global efforts. The country is taking important steps in the field of transition to renewable energy sources, reduction of carbon emissions and application of sustainable development principles to reduce the negative impacts of climate change. At the same time, it continues its efforts to fulfill its international obligations by solving economic and social challenges at the national level. Such activities can further strengthen Azerbaijan's role in global climate policy.

References

1. Dimeyeva, L. A., Sitpayeva, G. T., Sultanova, B. M., Ussen, K., & Islamgulova, A. F. (2015). High-altitude flora and vegetation of Kazakhstan and climate change impacts. *Climate change impacts on high-altitude ecosystems*, 1-48.
2. Isaev, A. P., Protopopov, A. V., Protopopova, V. V., Egorova, A. A., Timofeyev, P. A., Nikolaev, A. N., ... & Slepstova, N. P. (2010). *Vegetation of Yakutia: elements of ecology and plant sociology. The Far North: plant biodiversity and ecology of Yakutia*, 143-260.
3. Bilichenko, I. N. (2020). Influence of forest fires on mountain-taiga geosystems. In *Environmental transformation and sustainable development in the Asian region* (pp. 80-80).
4. Эльшад, К., & Асланова, С. (2024). ИСТОРИЯ И ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ИЗУЧЕНИЯ ФИТОМЕЛИОРАЦИИ НЕФТЕЗАГРЯЗНЕННЫХ ЗЕМЕЛЬ В АЗЕРБАЙДЖАНЕ. *German International Journal of Modern Science/Deutsche Internationale Zeitschrift für Zeitgenössische Wissenschaft*, (80).
5. Basti, A., & Aslanova, F. (2024). THE RELATIVE DORMANCY OF NEWLY INTRODUCED PEACH CULTIVARS CHARACTERISTIC. *Annali d'Italia* №, 60, 10.
6. Qurbanov, E. M., & Cabbarov, M. T. (2017). *Geobotany*. Baku: Baku State University publishing house.
7. Qurbanov, E. M. (2009). *Medicinal plants*. Baku: Elm.
8. Azizi, A., Mahboob, M., Monib, A. W., Hassand, M. H., Sediqi, S., & Niazi, P. (2023). The Role of Plants in Human Health. *British Journal of Biology Studies*, 3(1), 08-12.
9. Qurbanov, E. M. (1996). *Plant world of Nakhichevanchay river basin*. Baku: Baku State University, 248.
10. Qurbanov, E., & Huseynova, H. (2022). New spreading areas of some species in the Botanicalgeographical regions of the middle part of the Caspian coast. *Acta Botanica Caucasica*. Published by Baku State University, Department of Botany and Plant Physiology. Volum, 1, 4-8.
11. Youssef, N., Markert, B., Qurbanov, E., Sevnic, H., & Wünschmann, S. (2014). Bioindication of trace metal pollution in the atmosphere of Baku city using *ligustrum japonicum*, *olea europea*, and *pyracantha coccinea* leaves. *Journal of Environmental*

Engineering and Landscape Management, 22(1), 14-20.

12. Abdallah, Y. N., & Mejnun, G. E. (2013). Change of The Morpho-Anatomical Structure of Leaves of *Ligustrum japonicum* And *Olea europea* Caused By Heavy Metal Pollution. *Caspian Journal of Applied Sciences Research*, 2(2).

13. Atamov, V. V., Cabbarov, M., & Gurbanov, E. (2006). The pytosociological characteristics of ecosystems of mountain of Talysh Region of Azerbaijan. *Asian Journal of Plant Sciences*, 5(5), 899-904.

14. Gurbanov, E., & Aslanova, S. (2024). AVERAGE ANNUAL PRODUCTIVITY OF THE THYMUS-ETALUM-FESTUCOSUM FORMATION, DISTRIBUTED IN SUMMER PASTURE FIELD NO. 8 "TURKESOBA"(AZERBAIJAN). *Norwegian Journal of Development of the International Science*, 126.

15. Kurbanov, E., Aslanova, S., & Ibragimov, S. (2023). Types of Hole-Meadow and Wetlands Vegetation in Oil-contaminated Soils Siyazan District (Azerbaijan). *Bulletin of Science and Practice*.

16. Gurbanov, E., Aslanova, S., & Ibrahimov, S. (2023). The Alhagieto-Salsoletum-Artemisiosum formation group at the SiyazanNeft NQCI mine. *AS-Proceedings*, 1(3), 17.

17. Эльшад, К., & Санубар, А. (2024). ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКАЯ КЛАССИФИКАЦИЯ ПОЧВЕННО-РАСТИТЕЛЬНЫХ ТЕРРИТОРИЙ, ЗАГРЯЗНЕННЫХ МИНЕРАЛИЗОВАННЫМИ ВОДАМИ НА АПСХЕРОНСКОМ ПОЛУОСТРОВЕ. *German International Journal of Modern Science/Deutsche Internationale Zeitschrift für Zeitgenössische Wissenschaft*, (75).

18. Gurbanov, E., & Aslanova, S. (2023). Phytocenoses found in grassy mountain-meadow soils in the subalpine zone of Talish.

19. Gurbanov, E. M., Sh, A. S., & Asadova, B. Q. (2023). PHYTOECOLOGICAL RESEARCH ON OIL-CONTAMINATED SOILS OF "SHIRVANNEFT" OIL AND GAS DEVELOPMENT AREA AND ITS RECULTIVATION (AZERBAIJAN). *Труды Мордовского государственного природного заповедника им. П.Г. Смидовича*, (33), 172-183.

20. Qurbanov, E., Aslanova, S., & Ibrahimov, Ş. (2024). ŞİRVAN RAYONUNUN NEFTLƏ ÇİRKƏNMIŞ TORPAQLARINDA RAST GƏLİNƏN YARIMSƏHRA BİTKİLİYİNİN FİTOEKOLOJİ XARAKTERİSTİKASI. *Nature & Science/Təbiət və Elm*, 6(1).

21. Гурбанов, Э., Асланов, С., & Сафарова, А. (2024). КЛИМАТИЧЕСКИЕ УСЛОВИЯ ГОРНОЙ ЧАСТИ ТАЛЫША. *German International Journal of Modern Science/Deutsche Internationale Zeitschrift für Zeitgenössische Wissenschaft*, (90).

22. Aslanova, S. (2024). Subalpine Meadow Vegetation of Talish Highlands of Azerbaijan.

23. GURBANOV, E., & RZAYEVA, A. EVALUATION OF DECORATIVE PROPERTIES OF SOME CONIFEROUS PLANTS INTRODUCED TO ABSHERON PENINSULA.

24. Yusifova, A., Asadova, B., & Aslanova, S. (2024). PLANTS, HUMAN HEALTH AND CIVILIZATION. *Norwegian Journal of Development of the International Science*, 136.

25. Асланова, Ф. (2024). АГРОБИОЛОГИЧЕСКАЯ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКА РАЗЛИЧНЫХ СОРТОВ КУКУРУЗЫ, ВЫРАЩИВАЕМЫХ В БОГАРНЫХ УСЛОВИЯХ ЗАКАТАЛЫ, И РОЛЬ В СЕЛЕКЦИИ. <https://www.bulletennauki.ru>, 102.